

The Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model as a Panacea for Effective Teaching in Nigerian Colleges of Education

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Abstract

This study examined unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model as panacea to effective teaching and quality education in Nigerian Colleges of Education. The study was a descriptive research of survey type. The population of lecturers was 1,320 and 258 lecturers were sampled with only 255 completely returned the instruments. The Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in selecting samples with (182 males, 73 female lecturers). Descriptive statistics were used to answer research questions while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Bonferoni's post-hoc analysis was used to locate direction of differences in Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model (UTAUT) for teaching to enhance quality education for best practices in South-west Nigerian COEs. Two major objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses were involved in the study. Findings revealed that lecturers had adequate access, relevant computer competency and positive attitude towards application of Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model for teachings; lecturers' gender had no influence on access to online tools but area of specialization influenced application of (UTAUT). The study concluded that lecturers had access to online tools, and it was recommended that (UTAUT) could be incorporated into teaching in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

Keywords: Unified Theory, Technology Model, Effective Teaching and Quality Education.

Introduction

With the advent of new communication models in technologies, there is a common understanding that the world has become globalized and knowledge is shared and distributed with relative ease. Actually, the evolution of computers and media in education has forced the re-examination of what is worth knowing and by extension, how to share the knowledge with others. (Heinich, Molenda, Russell and Smaldino, 2002; Singh, Sharma and Upadhyya, 2008). Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is an information system (IS) theory that models how users come to accept the use of technology. The model suggests that when users are presented with new technology, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it; hence TAM is generally referred to as the most influential and commonly employed theory in information theory (Lee, Kozar & Larson, 2003) in Olasedidun, (2014).

Figure 1: Technology Acceptance Model Source: Davis (1989)

TAM replaces many of TRA's attitude measure with the two technology acceptance measure of perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). TAM is specifically the development with primary aim of identifying the determinants involved in computer technology acceptance in general; secondly, to examine a variety of information technology usage behaviours and thirdly, to provide a parsimonious theoretical explanatory model (Bertrand & Bouchard, 2008). TRA and TAM, both have strong behavioral elements, that when someone forms an intention to act, that they will be free to act without limitation, though in reality many constraints such as freedom to act could be limited.

TAM has led researchers to examine the task of explaining and predicting user acceptance of new computer and information technology in the organizational context (Janelle, 2006). However, perceived usefulness of computer is a widely used variable in studies of technology use in a working environment (Mc Gill, Klobas & Renzi, 2011). It has been confirmed by researchers that TAM has been of help in gaining improved significance in studies of computer use in the educational domain as well Friedrich & Haron, (2010). For instance, Eli (2008) researched into perceived ease of use and usefulness of social media by undergraduate students, using a measure of the concepts of perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology for social networking media with regard to the ease of use and usefulness in technology dimensions context from the factor analysis it was revealed from the respondents, that higher perceived ease of use led to higher perceived usefulness and ultimately greater intensity of use of the social networking media.

The application of Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model by lecturers in Nigerian Colleges of Education requires technical expertise, attitudinal behaviors, accessibility level measurements and other intervening variables such as gender, school type and age ranges among others to be critically and empirically assessed.

The TAM with two variations of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) to determine which model is the most helpful in understanding the technology usage while Venkatesh, Morris and Davis (2003) expanded TAM by building a new model known as Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Technology acceptance model (TAM) has proven to be a theoretical model in helping to explain and predict users' behaviours towards information technology. The UTAUT contains four core determinants variables of intention and usage. These are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions. UTAUT also defined another four moderator variables that influence the core determinants variables which are gender, age, experience and voluntariness of use thus, in this work, the researcher is of the opinion that adhering to the generic DITI, TAM & UTAUT might occasioned to inconsistency hence the adapted model is utilised.

Figure 2: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Figure 3: Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (AUTAUT)

This study found out the relevance of application of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model as a panacea for effective teaching purposes by lecturers in South-west Nigerian Colleges of Education for quality education and national development to not only change the world but also change the way the world changes with respect to the teaching and learning process in the Nigerian Colleges of Education.

Statement of the Problem

It is of note that the decline in quality of education in Nigeria might not be unconnected with the old traditional teaching techniques of lecturers and poor habit exhibited by students (Ofodu, 2007). Also, (Gambari, 2012), contended that teachers seldom use computer online tools for teaching even where they are available while (Adebayo, 2011) conducted a research on secondary school teachers' perception of ICT and revealed that teachers' perception of ICT is low and are not using computer or integrating ICT into the teaching-learning process.

This study on relevance of the Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model as a panacea for effective teaching purposes by lecturers South-west Nigerian Colleges of Education for quality education and national development would be a paradigm shift from the "traditional" ways of teaching and learning that is no longer sufficient in producing knowledge and skills at a speed, variety and quality necessary to make them relevant, competitive and profitable in this new knowledge economy for the digital natives and the digital migrants.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to find out the relevance of the Adapted Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (AUTAUT) model in online tools usage for teaching purposes by lecturers in South-west Nigerian Colleges of Education.

1. Examined Colleges of Education lecturers' access to online tools for enhancing teaching with AUTAUT model;
2. Examined attitude of lecturers to online tools application for teaching using AUTAUT.

Research Questions

- I. How accessible are the online tools for teaching by COE lecturers?
- II. What is the attitude of lecturers towards access to online tools for teaching?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers in the access to online tools using AUTAUT model.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers in their attitude towards using (AUTAUT) model.

The test reliability was done and following Crombach's Alpha value were realized: $r = 0.96$ and $r = 0.89$ for the lecturers' access and attitude towards online tools application using AUTAUT Model for teaching respectively. The overall reliability of lecturers' instrument is $r = 0.89$.

Research Question One

How accessible are the online tools for teaching by lecturers in Colleges of Education?

Table 1: Access to Online Tools by Lecturers

S/N	Items	Lecturers Mean & SD	
		Mean	SD
1	I have access to online tools at home.	3.21	.768
2	I have access to online tools in my office in the college.	2.45	1.045
3	The ICT infrastructure are provided to support online tools usage for teaching in my college.	2.21	1.234
4	I have access to a computer with adequate software at the college (e.g. Microsoft Word, Power Point, Adobe Acrobat).	2.38	1.000
5	Electricity power supply is available adequately to support online tools application in my college.	2.05	1.567
6	I check my e-mail at least once a week..	3.03	0.876
7	My college has adequate support services for the online tools application.	2.40	1.092
8	Electricity power supply is available adequately to support online tools application in my home.	2.56	.996
9	I have access to a computer with adequate software at home (e.g. Microsoft Word, Power Point, and Adobe Acrobat).	2.82	1.010
10	I use online tools to give assignments to students often.	2.24	1,211
	Grand Mean on Access	2.53	0.434

Table 1 presents the results on the access to Online tools by lecturers. The results revealed mean score on lecturers' access to online tools, using a benchmark of 2.50 for each item. It is therefore deduced that lecturers have access to online tools at home with mean score of 3.21. However, lecturers have limited access to online tools in the office in the college with mean score of 2.45. Most of the lecturers check their e-mail at least once a week with mean score of 3.03. Electricity power supply is available adequately to support online tools application in the homes of lecturers with mean score of 2.56 and lecturers had access to a computer with adequate software at home (e.g. Microsoft Word, Power Point, Adobe Acrobat) with mean score of 2.82.

However, lecturers disagree that the ICT infrastructure are provided to support online tools usage for teaching in their college with mean score of 2.21. Majority of the lecturers had no access to a computer with adequate software/program at the college (e.g. Microsoft Word, Power Point, Adobe Acrobat) with mean score of 2.38 and Electricity power supply is unavailable adequately to support online tools application in lecturers' office with mean score of 2.05. Most college have low adequate support services for the online tools application with mean score of 2.40 and lecturers occasionally use online tools to give assignments to students often with mean score of 2.24. With a grand mean score of 2.53 and grand variance of standard deviation of 0.434 which is a bit higher than the 2.50 benchmark, it can be concluded that lecturers have moderate access to online tools.

Research Question Two

What is the attitude of lecturers towards the application of online tools for teaching using UTAUT?

The analysis on the attitude of lecturers towards the application of online tools for teaching using UTAUT Model reviewed in table2

Table 2: Attitude of Lecturers

S/N	Items	Lecturers Mean & SD	
		Mean	SD
1	I am willing to use electronic learning Software in daily learning tasks.	3.33	.603
2	Online tools could make work more interesting.	3.50	.560
3	I prefer face-to-face lessons with my lectures.	2.89	.759
4	I believe that self-development in technology may strengthen my learning task	3.49	.588
5	Online tools application could increase my daily productivity in learning	3.33	.564
6	Application of online tools eliminate eye contact and reduce learners' seriousness.	2.98	.856
7	I am skillfully ready to use online tools for learning	3.11	.601
8	I use variety of online tools for specific purpose in learning.	2.70	.680
9	My application of online tools has enhanced my professional communication competency.	2.90	.559
10	The application of online tools has increased my reasoning ability.	3.00	.599
	Grand Mean on Lecturers Attitude	3.13	.367

Table 2 revealed that majority of the respondents believe that online tools could make teaching more interesting with mean score of 3.50, and they also believe that self-development in technology may strengthen learning task with mean score of 3.49. Also with mean score of 3.33, it can be deduced that lecturers are willing to use electronic learning Software in daily teaching tasks and online tools application could increase their daily productivity in learning. Lecturers are skillfully ready to use online tools for teaching and the application of online tools had increased lecturers' reasoning ability with mean scores of 3.11 and 3.00 respectively. A mean score of 2.98 established that the application of online tools eliminates eye contact and reduce learners' seriousness. Also, the application of online tools has enhanced lecturers' professional communication competency through mean score of 2.90. However, some lecturers still prefer face-to-face lessons with lectures with a mean score of 2.89. Lecturers use variety of online tools for specific purpose in learning with mean score of 2.70. Convincingly, with a grand mean score of 3.13, lecturers have upright attitude towards the application of online tools for teaching.

Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching using AUTAUT Model.

In determining whether there exist any significant differences between male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching. Independent t-test was used to test the null hypothesis and this is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: t-test on male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching

Gender	N	Df	Mean	Std.Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Male	182	253	2.558791	.3712078	1.629	.105
Female	73		2.471233	.4270309		
Total	255					

As indicated in Table 3, $t(253) = 1.63$, $p > .05$. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This is because the result of the t-value of 1.63 resulting in 0.11 significance value was greater than 0.05 alpha value. This implies that the null hypothesis, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching using AUTAUT

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' attitude in applying online tools for teaching using AUTAUT.

Table 4: t-test analysis on male and female lecturers' attitude

Gender	N	Df	Mean	Std.Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Male	182	253	3.113187	.3491770	-0.818	0.414
Female	73		3.154795	.4089421		
Total	255					

Table 4 presented analysis on significant difference between male and female lecturers' attitude towards the application of online tools. The results showed that $t(253) = 0.818$, $p > .05$. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This is because the result of the t-value of 0.818 resulting in 0.414 significance value was greater than 0.05 alpha value. Therefore, the null hypothesis, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' attitude towards the application of online tools for learning was not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' attitude towards the application of online tools.

Discussions

The findings established that colleges of education lecturers have positive attitudes towards utilization of AUTAUT Model online tools. Nigeria colleges of education this supports the researchers submissions that use of online tools is currently considered the most popular platform for social networking among higher education lecturers. It also shows there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' access to online tools for teaching.

Furthermore, there is no significant difference between lecturers' application of online tools using AUTAUT Model for teaching based on gender but despite the potential benefits of collaborative learning, like development of critical thinking skills, co-creation of knowledge and meaningful reflection and trans-formative learning, these collaborative tools are yet to be put into full utilization.

There is significant difference between access to and application of online tools by lecturers working in federal institutions, state institutions and private institutions as indicated certain essential connections: first, a strong social presence through timely feedback, interaction with facilitators, peer-to-peer contact, discussion forums, and collaborative activities; second, technological facets technology access, online learning, self-efficacy, and computer self-efficacy; and thirdly, tools (web sites, video clips).

Conclusions and Recommendations

- i. Lecturers have access to online tools for teaching.
- ii. Lecturers have positive attitude towards the application of AUTAUT Model for teaching.
- iii. Lecturers' gender had no influence on their application of online tools using UTAUT Model for teaching.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Colleges of Education school ownership's should make adequate provisions of ICT facilities with adequate online tools affordable for lecturers in Nigerian Colleges of Education. This will improve teaching and learning.
2. Constant seminars and workshop on the relevance of online tools adoption strategies for teaching using the adapted model of UTAUT should be organized for lecturers to update knowledge acquisitions.

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